

Funding liquidity and bank lending: Evidence from Vietnam

Van Dan Dang

Department of Finance, Banking University of Ho Chi Minh city

corresponding e-mail: [dandv1978\[at\]yahoo\(dot\)com](mailto:dandv1978[at]yahoo(dot)com)

address: 36 Ton That Dam street, Nguyen Thai Binh ward, District 1, Ho Chi Minh city, Vietnam

Abstract: This study examines the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending in terms of loan growth, using a dataset of commercial banks in Vietnam, an emerging country over the period from 2003 to 2017. The empirical results by GMM estimator to control dynamic nature of panel data model show that banks owning higher funding liquidity measured by higher ratios of deposit tend to lend more. Further analysis also strongly suggests that bank capital usually mitigates the impact of funding liquidity on loan growth. In addition, this study gives some evidence that bank size tends to strengthen the impact of funding liquidity on loan growth. These empirical findings are still robust with an alternative regression technique. The study adds some arguments to the debate about the role of funding liquidity on bank lending behaviour in emerging markets, particularly considering the interaction impact of bank specific characteristics. Bank managers as well as policymakers could rely on presented implications to improve the banking regulatory and practical framework to better operation.

JEL Classifications: C23, G21, G32

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1. Introduction

Bank regulators have acknowledged the essential power of sufficient funding liquidity. They establish regulations which require banks to have adequate funding liquidity, insuring against small liquidity shocks (Kim & Sohn, 2017). However, it is not absolutely certain whether the concentration on these funding liquidity requirements applied widely could help banks reduce risks and the whole financial system gain more stability (Khan et al., 2017).

Some authors have laid the foundation for studying the effect of funding liquidity on bank lending. Among them, we have to mention Acharya & Naqvi (2012), who present a theoretical framework to suggest that lower funding liquidity risk encourages bank managers to involve in lending activities more aggressively. Previously, Ivashina & Scharfstein (2010) reveal that during the global financial crisis from 2007 to 2008, greater access to deposit funding urged banks to lend more than those relied more on other short-term debt financing. Although this issue is considered greatly by researchers, most studies have focused mainly on developed countries rather than emerging ones. Moreover, to the best of our knowledge, no prior study has empirically examined this field in an emerging country comprehensively as Vietnam so far.

Under the tight control on loan decisions of governments, banks in emerging countries often decrease their lending activities (Qian et al., 2015). Studying bank lending behaviour

in these countries is interesting and Vietnam is completely not an exception. Vietnam owns an open and globally integrating economy, based on high economic growth as well as macroeconomic and political stability (Vo, 2016). Contrary to the development of the economy, the nascent banking sector in Vietnam has faced many difficulties and challenges recently. Vietnamese banking system is featured by the domination of the state banks (Batten & Vo, 2016) as well as large banks. Credit quality and bad debt handling are becoming very concerned issues. Besides, the State Bank of Vietnam has advocated the pilot application of Basel II standards for some commercial banks, aiming to comprehensively apply Basel II and further Basel III in the future.

The study aims at investigating how funding liquidity affects lending behaviour of commercial banks in terms of loan growth in an emerging market, more specially exploring some determinants of this impact. We expect that the dynamic panel approach to capture the nature of bank lending behaviour will provide reliable empirical evidences. The study's idea is relatively related to some current literature in exploring funding liquidity and bank lending behaviour. For example, Khan et al. (2017) investigate the impact of funding liquidity risk on risk-taking behaviour through a sample of banks in developed countries. Dahir et al. (2018) explore funding liquidity risk in BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa) with a sample of publicly listed banks. However, our study has some different features. The study concentrates on one particular emerging country which applies a unified accounting system, instead of focusing on various countries with differences in accounting standards and information transparency problems. The study also employs relatively big dataset for the period of 2003 - 2017 with observations on all Vietnamese commercial banks, instead of focusing on listed banks which are very different from the other banks in the same system. More interestingly, the effects of bank-specific factors such as capital, size and state ownership are also considered to have influence on the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending measured by loan growth. Besides, to check robustness, we use the GDP growth and the inflation rate as macroeconomic conditions that affect bank lending behaviour.

This study has some contributions. First, it extends the current literature on funding liquidity and bank lending, especially for emerging countries. Second, it finds out the interaction effects of bank capital, bank size with funding liquidity on bank lending, which has not received much attention from researchers. Third, it provides both banks and governments with insightful information to have better strategies and policies. A better understanding of funding liquidity, bank lending behaviour and other bank-specific factors could motivate policymakers to improve the banking regulatory framework, to control the behaviour of bank managers and to enhance financial stability for the whole banking system. This is particularly useful in the context that banking system in Vietnam is aiming to perfect the standards of Basel II currently and further Basel III in the long term.

The remainder of this study is organized as follows. Section 2 summarises the relevant current literature and then establishes the hypotheses. Section 3 presents empirical models and describes the data before results and discussions are reported in Section 4. Section 5 provides the final conclusions.

2. Literature review and hypothesis development

Existing studies show a large interest in funding liquidity to serve the banks' liquidity risk management. For example, the relatively comprehensive study of Drehmann & Nikolaou

(2013) suggest that funding liquidity represents the bank's ability to meet to depositors' withdrawal requests immediately, whereas funding liquidity risk occurs when the bank fails to settle the depositors' claims immediately. Banks obtain funding liquidity from different sources, however, most people believe that funding liquidity of banks strongly relates to deposits. Nguyen & Phan (2018) measure funding liquidity in their study by the rate of total deposits to total bank assets. Khan et al. (2017) consider higher deposit rate to be lower funding liquidity risk for banks as well as to help them have sufficient funds to meet the obligations. These determinations show similarities with arguments of Drehmann & Nikolaou (2013) as they also suggest that funding liquidity may show funding liquidity risk. Overall, we originate the study relying on these definitions and suggestions.

Many scholars have paid their attention on the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending behaviour. Theoretically, Acharya & Naqvi (2012) argue that when banks have large source of deposits from customers, this will bring them lower funding liquidity risk and bank managers are encouraged to aggressively lower the lending interest rates, aiming to increase loan volumes as well as to improve their own market shares. The criteria for assessing the performance of bank managers is partially based on the amount of loans granted to customers, thus banks with large amount of deposits are easy to complete the loan growth targets and their managers will have more benefits. Moreover, short-term executives of banks may not consider long-term risks. Thereby, Acharya & Naqvi (2012) conclude that there exists a positive impact of funding liquidity and bank lending, implying that adequate funding liquidity leads banks to expand their lending activities. This is easier to explain in the context that banks are the primary engines of the whole economy as well as the motivation for higher economic growth (Berger et al., 2017). In addition, Ivashina & Scharfstein (2010) also state that banks significantly reduce their lending activities in case they are vulnerable to credit line drawdowns and not able to maintain sufficient funding liquidity.

However, there is some evidence in the existing literature to support a potential negative impact of funding liquidity on loan growth that we are investigating. For instance, Cornett et al. (2011) argue that despite having high rate of funding liquidity, loan growth of banks decreases in order to meet higher liquidity requirements from regulations. Accordingly, banks are required to maintain adequate liquidity to settle potential liquidity risks. Sufficient liquidity may help banks less likely to face lacking of liquidity and limit the risk of receiving central bank's support. As a result, banks may restrict their credit activities in accordance with liquidity requirements in terms of maintaining higher funding liquidity. Thereby, in this situation we could observe the negative association between funding liquidity and bank lending. Besides, to maintain a higher stable funding liquidity ratio, King (2013) recognizes that banks need to pay higher interest rates for depositors to borrow more long-term funds. By this way, increased deposit interest rates (input) lead to increased lending interest rates (output) and thereby reducing the demand of loans.

Much of the empirical literature has investigated the relationship between several bank-specific and macroeconomic factors on bank lending. These factors have substantial impacts on bank lending behaviour (Ferri et al., 2014; Zuzana et al., 2014; Matousek & Solomon, 2018; Vo, 2018). Whereas there are other studies which partially explore funding liquidity and lending behaviour of banks (Louhichi & Boujelbene, 2017; Dahir et al., 2018). Limited literature focuses mainly on the effect of funding liquidity on bank lending in terms of loan growth, especially in an emerging country as Vietnam. Hence, we revisit some relevant empirical literature to finally develop the hypotheses.

Vazquez & Federico (2015) examine funding structures from the run-up to the global financial crisis and their effects on financial stability. By using a dataset of 11,000 banks in the US and Europe for the period of 2001-2009, they state that banks with insufficient liquidity before the crisis were more likely to face their default risk which leads to excessive risk-taking behaviours. Khan et al. (2017) use a dataset of US bank holding companies from 1986 to 2014 in order to examine the relationship between funding liquidity and bank risk-taking. Their results show that higher funding liquidity increases bank risk.

Dahir et al. (2018) estimate the association between funding liquidity risk, liquidity risk and risk-taking behaviour of publicly listed banks in BRICS countries from 2006 to 2015. They prove that liquidity risk and funding liquidity risk are negatively correlated with bank risk-taking. Ibrahim & Rizvi (2018) test the pattern of loan growth at conventional and Islamic banks during crisis time. They use a dataset of 114 banks across 10 countries. Their results show that bank lending at conventional banks declined during the global financial crisis, while bank lending at Islamic banks was unchanged. Islamic banks have higher rate of loan growth than conventional banks and deposits have no significant effect on bank lending during stress times.

In general, the current literature providing both theoretical and empirical evidences does not show the absolute consistency of the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending. However, originating from the arguments of Acharya & Naqvi (2012), we have the hypothesis as follows:

Hypothesis 1. *Banks owning higher funding liquidity will have incentives to lend more.*

So far, there has been little attention to the interaction role of bank-specific factors including capital, size and especially state ownership on the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending. First, a key factor in risk management and regulatory requirement for banks is capital. Kim & Sohn (2017) suggest that insufficient capital usually limits banks to issue loans. Bank capital reduces the probability of defaults, so banks with a risky portfolio have to maintain a high bank capital ratio (Shim, 2013). From a certain angle, bank capital may be seen as an additional source along with deposits to develop lending activities, although bank capital is more expensive to raise than deposits. To discuss about the costs of bank capital, Hyun & Rhee (2011) provide evidence that banks are willing to minimize high-risk assets instead of issuing new equity to increase capital ratios. In addition, holding adequate capital is better to cover losses that may come from selling illiquid investments for repayment of due liabilities (Distinguin et al., 2013). Hence, the capital ratio of banks is expected to mitigate the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending.

Hypothesis 2. *The ratio of bank capital tends to mitigate the effect of funding liquidity on bank lending.*

Regarding bank size, as banks become larger, their funding strategy and loan composition tend to change. Larger banks are expected to bear lower costs (lower risk compensation required) and have a greater chance to create funding source by non-deposit or wholesale funding (Bertay et al., 2013), while still ensuring their loan growth. Thereby, the interaction impact between bank size and bank funding liquidity on loan growth is expected to be negative, indicating that large banks are less dependent on funding liquidity than small banks to expand their lending.

Hypothesis 3. *The bank size tends to reduce the effect of funding liquidity on bank lending.*

The Vietnamese banking system is not only dominated by large banks, but also by banks with a large proportion of state ownership. With the advantages of deposits and many other sources of capital, state-owned commercial banks always have better lending interest-rate basis than private commercial banks. Lending as well as deposit mobilization strategies of these banks may be different from others in the same system. As King (2013) suggests that banks usually have more expensive deposits through borrowing more long-term funds to maintain a higher stable funding liquidity ratio, this may seem incompletely true for state-owned banks in Vietnam when they could easily mobilize deposits with low interest rates. Thus, we expect state-owned banks to be less sensitive to funding liquidity than private banks in terms of lending expansion.

Hypothesis 4. *The state ownership tends to mitigate the effect of funding liquidity on bank lending.*

3. Methodology

3.1. Model

To achieve research objectives, we apply the dynamic panel approach to set up the baseline model as follows:

$$LGR_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta \times LGR_{i,t-1} + \gamma \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \delta \times Bank_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

where β , γ and δ are coefficients, while $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ represents the error term for bank i in year t

The dependent variable is LGR , which measures the growth rate in loan volume from bank i in year t relative to year $t-1$. Loan growth rate is a very important factor for Vietnamese economy in the context of very strict management from government. This variable has been widely employed for research in the bank lending literature (Jimborean, 2009; Gambacorta & Marques-Ibanez, 2011; Vo, 2018). We add one-year lag of this variable as an independent variable in order to capture the persistence effects of the dependent variable, consistent with many previous studies.

The independent variable is LIQ , a funding liquidity measure, calculated by the ratio of total deposits to total assets (Khan et al., 2017; Nguyen & Phan, 2018). We are assuming a lagged impact of funding liquidity on bank lending, this means that high funding liquidity increases the bank lending next year.

$Bank$ is a vector of control variables, including bank-specific factors: CAP is a proxy for bank capital measured by total bank equity divided by total assets, $SIZE$ represents bank size which is calculated as the natural logarithm of the total assets, $RISK$ is a proxy for bank risk measured by the rate of provisions for credit risk to total loans and ROA is a proxy of bank profitability which is calculated as the net income on total assets.

It takes time for portfolio to change and reflect decisions made on the historical events. From a risk management perspective, the foundation from previous factors may build a framework for bank decisions in terms of determining current lending behaviour (Roulet,

2018). Thus, we also employ all bank-specific explanatory variables lagged once in our models.

Next, to examine the impact of funding liquidity on lending behaviour in large banks, state-owned banks and to see how bank capital effects this relationship, we incorporate the interaction effects by adding to Equation (1) three interaction terms, separately, between funding liquidity and capital, size and state ownership of banks to establish Equation (2), (3) and (4) respectively. In which, *sizedum* is the dummy variable equal to 1 for banks whose average total assets are larger than the median size of the sample and 0 otherwise; *statedum* is the dummy variable taking a value of 1 for state-owned banks and 0 otherwise. The empirical models are re-specified as follows:

$$LGR_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta \times LGR_{i,t-1} + \gamma \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \delta \times Bank_{i,t-1} + \varphi \times CAP_{i,t-1} \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (2)$$

$$LGR_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta \times LGR_{i,t-1} + \gamma \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \delta \times Bank_{i,t-1} + \varphi \times sizedum_{i,t-1} \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

$$LGR_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta \times LGR_{i,t-1} + \gamma \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \delta \times Bank_{i,t-1} + \varphi \times statedum_i \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (4)$$

For robustness checks, we examine the impact of funding liquidity on lending behaviour of banks under the effect of macroeconomic factors. We continue to extend the equations by adding macroeconomic factors including *GDP* (the GDP growth rate) and *INF* (a proxy for inflation rate). These macroeconomic factors control for the business environment and have been widely employed in current literature (Berger & Udell, 1994; Khan et al., 2017; Vo, 2018). We also take one-year lag of these macroeconomic variables. Hence, the models are set up as follows, in which *Macro* is a vector of macroeconomic factors including *GDP* and *INF*:

$$LGR_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta \times LGR_{i,t-1} + \gamma \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \delta \times Bank_{i,t-1} + \lambda \times Macro_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (5)$$

$$LGR_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta \times LGR_{i,t-1} + \gamma \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \delta \times Bank_{i,t-1} + \varphi \times CAP_{i,t-1} \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \lambda \times Macro_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (6)$$

$$LGR_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta \times LGR_{i,t-1} + \gamma \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \delta \times Bank_{i,t-1} + \varphi \times sizedum_{i,t-1} \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \lambda \times Macro_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (7)$$

$$LGR_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta \times LGR_{i,t-1} + \gamma \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \delta \times Bank_{i,t-1} + \varphi \times statedum_i \times LIQ_{i,t-1} + \lambda \times Macro_{i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (8)$$

3.2. Estimation method

We employ the dynamic panel approach to allow for the dynamic nature of our model specification, which investigates the nature of bank lending behaviour. In the dynamic panel model, the lagged dependent variable is endogenous in case the sample covers micro panel data (small T and large N dimension). We estimate models considering the

generalized method of moments (GMM) to address the biasedness and inconsistency. This estimation method is considered more efficient than two-stage least squares (2SLS) regression because it accounts for the heteroscedasticity (Hall, 2005) as well as control for the endogeneity problem (Arellano & Bover, 1995) in the estimation models.

The estimation results are validated through Arellano-Bond test for the autocorrelation of the error term component and the Sargan test for the validity of the set of instrument variables.

3.3. Data

To investigate the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending behaviours, we use a dataset of Vietnamese commercial banks constructed on a yearly basis from 2003 and 2017. The sample excludes banks that have been bought by the State Bank of Vietnam, as well as the merged and consolidated banks in the study period. These banks have major fluctuations in operations and need time to stabilize, their financial data may have outliers. Also, bank with 5-year intermittent data is removed from the sample. Finally, collected banks include 31 commercial banks, in which we have one wholly state-owned bank, three state-private banks and 27 private banks. The financial data of banks is collected from Bankscope and Vietstock. In addition, we obtain the macroeconomic data from World Indicators development database of World Bank. The final sample including both listed and unlisted banks constitutes an unbalanced dataset with 358 observations due to lack of data in several years.

TABLE 1. SUMMARY STATISTICS

	DESCRIPTION	MEAN	STD. DEV.	MIN	MAX
<i>DEPENDENT VARIABLE</i>					
<i>LGR</i>	growth rate of bank loan	21.795	18.386	-45.548	91.881
<i>EXPLANATORY VARIABLES</i>					
<i>LIQ</i>	total deposits / total assets	62.053	13.809	18.510	89.217
<i>CAP</i>	total bank equity / total assets	10.520	7.281	0.102	80.071
<i>SIZE</i>	natural logarithm of total assets	17.893	1.414	12.839	20.882
<i>RISK</i>	provisions for credit risk / total loans	1.507	2.484	0.012	43.968
<i>ROA</i>	net income on assets	0.842	0.706	-5.511	4.688
<i>GDP</i>	GDP growth rate	6.233	0.668	5.247	7.547
<i>INF</i>	inflation rate	8.113	5.876	0.878	23.116
<i>sizedum</i>	= 1 for banks whose average total assets are larger than the median size of the sample and 0 otherwise	0.500	0.500	0	1
<i>statedum</i>	= 1 for state-owned banks and 0 otherwise	0.167	0.374	0	1

Note: The total number of observations is 358.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for variables employed in the analysis. The average growth rate of bank loan for the sample is 21.79%. On average, the funding liquidity, capital, size, risk and profitability for our sample constitute 62.05%, 10.52%, 17.89 (measured by natural logarithm of the total assets), 1.50% and 0.84% respectively.

The standard deviation of growth rate of bank loan and funding liquidity for the sample is 18.38% and 13.80% respectively. Hence, we notice that Vietnamese commercial banks expand lending significantly during the research period, with a relatively large division of loan growth among banks. In addition, deposits tend to account for a large proportion in the funding structure of banks.

Table 2 presents correlation coefficients matrix between variables used in the study. It shows an initial general overview of the correlation between variables. All of the correlation coefficients are small (except for the obvious correlation nature of *SIZE* and *sizedum*), thus we strongly determine that the multicollinearity is not a major problem in our empirical analyses.

TABLE 2. CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS MATRIX

	<i>LGR</i>	<i>LIQ</i>	<i>CAP</i>	<i>SIZE</i>	<i>RISK</i>	<i>ROA</i>	<i>GDP</i>	<i>INF</i>	<i>sizedum</i>	<i>statedum</i>
<i>LGR</i>	1									
<i>LIQ</i>	-0.23	1								
<i>CAP</i>	0.11	-0.29	1							
<i>SIZE</i>	-0.29	0.41	-0.57	1						
<i>RISK</i>	-0.01	0.02	-0.13	0.13	1					
<i>ROA</i>	0.33	-0.15	0.31	-0.28	-0.07	1				
<i>GDP</i>	0.23	0.04	-0.08	-0.11	0.07	0.04	1			
<i>INF</i>	-0.12	-0.36	0.17	-0.22	0.00	0.21	-0.24	1		
<i>sizedum</i>	-0.24	0.35	-0.42	0.80	0.09	-0.21	-0.01	-0.20	1	
<i>statedum</i>	-0.13	0.23	-0.32	0.55	0.19	-0.08	0.11	-0.01	0.44	1

4. Empirical results and discussion

4.1. The overall effect of funding liquidity on bank lending

In this section, we present the regression results of the impact of the funding liquidity on bank lending of Vietnamese commercial banks in the period from 2003 to 2017, using GMM for regression as mentioned. The estimation results are shown in Table 3. Based on the results of Sargan test and Arellano-Bond test, we strongly confirm that all instruments are valid and the second-order autocorrelation is absent in our models. Therefore, we could firmly rely on these estimations for decision-making.

Overall, the regression models have shown the significant effects of variables on lending behaviour of banks measured by loan growth rate.

First, we observe that the lagged dependent variable shows the negative and significant impact on the dependent variable. This indicates that in case Vietnamese banks have high rate of loan growth in the current year, this rate in the next year tends to decelerate. This finding is important in terms of reflecting the lending behaviour and operation strategies in Vietnamese banks. The finding reinforces the study result of Vo (2018) which does not detect this impact with appropriate significance in Vietnamese commercial banks in the study period from 2006 to 2015.

TABLE 3. REGRESSION RESULTS

VARIABLE	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
LGR_{t-1}	-0.143 (0.027)***	-0.146 (0.035)***	-0.171 (0.041)***	-0.144 (0.028)***
LIQ_{t-1}	0.249 (0.043)***	0.791 (0.159)***	0.216 (0.030)***	0.264 (0.047)***
CAP_{t-1}	0.713 (0.114)***	3.281 (0.724)***	0.616 (0.118)***	0.743 (0.130)***
$SIZE_{t-1}$	-12.733 (0.400)***	-12.830 (0.294)***	-14.897 (1.359)***	-12.473 (0.472)***
$RISK_{t-1}$	0.170 (0.146)	0.081 (0.163)	0.068 (0.221)	0.174 (0.155)
ROA_{t-1}	-0.471 (1.803)	-3.840 (2.273)*	-1.012 (1.810)	-0.598 (1.933)
$CAP_{t-1} \times LIQ_{t-1}$		-0.045 (0.012)***		
$sizedum_{t-1} \times LIQ_{t-1}$			0.066 (0.030)**	
$statedum_{t-1} \times LIQ_{t-1}$				-0.295 (0.322)
Observations	294	294	294	294
AR(1) test	-2.894 (0.003)	-2.579 (0.009)	-2.477 (0.013)	-2.823 (0.004)
AR(2) test	-1.212 (0.225)	-1.558 (0.119)	-1.500 (0.133)	-1.230 (0.218)
Sargan test	28.720 (0.764)	22.462 (0.950)	25.632 (0.876)	0.744 (0.744)

Note: This table reports the GMM regression results of the equation (1), (2), (3) and (4) presented in column (1), (2), (3) and (4), respectively. Arellano-Bond test for the p-order autocorrelation (AR (p)) of error term (Z-test). Sargans test for the validity of instrument variables (χ^2 test). The symbols *, **, and *** represent statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% level, respectively.

The coefficient of LIQ variable with a one-year lag is positive and statistically significant at 1% level, showing the positive impact of funding liquidity on bank lending. This implies that the more funding liquidity banks have, the more likely they will expand their lending activities. This result is completely consistent with the study of Acharya & Naqvi (2012) and thus strongly confirms Hypothesis 1. Attracting more deposits has encouraged banks to invest in a primary channel as customer lending, in the context of the credit market in an emerging country as Vietnam has much of the potential to develop. Moreover, the bank managers' benefits may be an important factor as the explanation of Acharya & Naqvi (2012). The finding also shows that the financial strength and funding source of the bank are crucial since state authority in Vietnam determines the rate of credit growth relying on the evaluation of each commercial bank's safety and soundness (Vo, 2018).

Regarding control variables, the ratio of bank capital through CAP variable with a one-year lag indicates the significantly positive impact on bank lending of Vietnamese commercial banks at a significant level of 1%. This implies that higher ratio of bank capital is associated with higher lending growth. This finding is also consistent with the current empirical literature (Cohen & Scatigna, 2016; Kim & Sohn, 2017). For banks, especially Vietnamese banks, which are in the process of upgrading capital safety standards, ensuring

the necessary capital adequacy ratio is a prerequisite to develop lending activities and in case this capital ratio is guaranteed to increase, it is an important factor for banks to expand their lending.

Bank size's coefficient is negative and significant at the 1% level, highlighting that large banks tend to be more cautious in their lending behaviour while smaller banks have a tendency to extend more loan growth. This result is appropriate in the context that smaller banks' lending activities are almost riskier as well as explain the current problem of the Vietnamese banking system where some small banks have the high ratio of bad debt and are subject to be merged into larger banks (Vo, 2018).

In addition, regarding the factors that are expected to affect bank lending behaviour, the regression results show that representative variables are not statistically significant, including bank risk and bank profitability measured by *RISK* and *ROA* variables respectively.

4.2. The effects of capital, size and state ownership of banks on the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending

Interaction terms is set up to recognize the marginal impact of capital, size and state ownership of banks on the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending. The regression results from columns 2, 3 and 4 in Table 3 show that the estimated coefficients of interaction terms involving *CAP* and *sizedum* are negative (statistical significance at the level of 1%) and positive (statistical significance at the level of 5%), respectively. While the interaction term involving *statedum* does not show statistical significance.

The finding reveals that banks with higher capital ratios are less sensitive to the deposits to expand their lending. This result is completely consistent with our expectation as stated in Hypothesis 2. Whereas the finding also suggests that bank size strengthens the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending, not in line with our initial expectation in Hypothesis 3. A possible explanation is that large banks in Vietnam are under more pressure of state control, their capital adequacy ratios reach the ceiling and it is more difficult to expand other sources of capital rather than deposits to develop lending activities. This is also a prominent issue of Vietnamese banking system currently. The study results have contributed to the existing debates about the role of bank capital and bank size which affect the efficiency of funding liquidity and lending in Vietnam.

4.3. Robustness checks

Continue to employ GMM for regression with extended equations, our robust check results are presented in Table 4.

These results are almost consistent with the results without macroeconomic factors (see Table 3), except for dummy variable representing bank size characteristic which shows that the coefficient is not statistically significant in the sense it is still positive as in previous regression model.

Results in Table 4 show that GDP growth rate reduces loan growth whereas we do not find statistically significant evidence (at the level of 5%) about the effect of the inflation on bank lending. Surprisingly, this finding is not as our expectation in the context that the

economic growth of Vietnam implies the expansion of economic activities, which are usually accompanied by loan growth.

TABLE 4. REGRESSION RESULTS WITH MACROECONOMIC FACTORS

VARIABLE	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
LGR_{t-1}	-0.107 (0.033)***	-0.157 (0.044)***	-0.131 (0.037)***	-0.130 (0.034)***
LIQ_{t-1}	0.235 (0.028)***	0.828 (0.161)***	0.179 (0.043)***	0.217 (0.045)***
CAP_{t-1}	0.587 (0.066)***	3.430 (0.816)***	0.445 (0.158)***	0.551 (0.175)***
$SIZE_{t-1}$	-13.414 (0.841)***	-13.710 (1.116)***	-14.381 (1.113)***	-14.124 (0.817)***
$RISK_{t-1}$	0.184 (0.133)	0.180 (0.174)	0.210 (0.179)	0.187 (0.175)
ROA_{t-1}	-2.306 (1.931)	-1.412 (2.252)	-0.525 (2.066)	-1.934 (2.224)
$CAP_{t-1} \times LIQ_{t-1}$		-0.053 (0.014)***		
$sizedum_{t-1} \times LIQ_{t-1}$			0.023 (0.030)	
$statedum_{t-1} \times LIQ_{t-1}$				-0.075 (0.281)
GDP_{t-1}	-3.317 (0.589)***	-3.527 (0.667)***	-3.612 (0.685)***	-3.373 (0.669)***
INF_{t-1}	-0.104 (0.079)	-0.079 (0.073)	-0.129 (0.067)*	-0.163 (0.085)*
Observations	294	294	294	294
AR(1) test	-3.111 (0.001)	-2.450 (0.014)	-2.894 (0.003)	-2.909 (0.003)
AR(2) test	-1.141 (0.253)	-1.303 (0.192)	-1.049 (0.294)	-1.123 (0.261)
Sargan test	25.414 (0.882)	23.805 (0.924)	27.925 (0.796)	27.611 (0.808)

Note: This table reports the GMM regression results of the equation (5), (6), (7) and (8) presented in column (5), (6), (7) and (8), respectively. Arellano-Bond test for the p-order autocorrelation (AR (p)) of error term (Z-test). Sargan test for the validity of instrument variables (χ^2 test). The symbols *, **, and *** represent statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% level, respectively.

This finding has very important implications for monetary policy makers in Vietnam, a strongly developing country as well as call for in-depth studies in the future about the nexus between bank lending channel and economic growth. Monetary policy mainly through bank lending with the final aim of economic growth is particularly the key point for emerging countries and through our empirical results, we could observe the negative effect of economic growth on bank lending channel of the Vietnamese banking system.

5. Study limitations

In general, although the study has basically reached the targets set out with interesting results, our work still faces some limitations. This study as well as many other empirical studies in the similar field have not approached the specific definition of funding liquidity

in detail (Drehmann & Nikolaou (2013) may be one the very few exceptions as they try to define and measure the funding liquidity). We simply apply deposit rate to proxy funding liquidity without further discussion on the nature of funding liquidity as Drehmann & Nikolaou (2013) have done. In addition, the state ownership variable in our study is constant over time, thus the regression result of this variable are not shown due to the difference-taking process according to GMM estimator. This may partially affect the research result of the state ownership's interaction role and it is necessary to consider other regression methods to address this issue in future studies.

6. Conclusions

The study investigates the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending behaviour of Vietnamese commercial banks over the period from 2003 to 2017. The finding reveals that funding liquidity has a positive impact on bank lending, implying funding liquidity increases the loan growth rate of banks. The study also examines the interaction effect of bank-specific factors including capital, size and state ownership on the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending. The results suggest that capital ratio of banks tend to reduce the studying impact while bank size shows the opposite effect, though this evidence is relatively weak compared to other findings. Besides, we could not find the empirical evidence to confirm the influence of state ownership on the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending. The results are almost consistent with all estimation equations with or without macroeconomic factors.

Through these empirical evidences, the study implies that funding liquidity could lead to expand bank lending activities and thereby to improve profitability as well as to achieve the expected targets for banks. This may have implications for banks in terms of funding structures and risk managements. At the same time, banks have to pay great attention to bank-specific factors such as bank capital and bank size which also play important roles in explaining the impact of funding liquidity on bank lending. These results also offer policymakers in Vietnam insightful information to strengthen the orientation in developing capital adequacy regulations for commercial banks.

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